

Modeling the Entrepreneurial Interest of Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri

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Abstract:- One of the reasons for the increase in the number of unemployed in Indonesia is diploma and undergraduate graduates who generally prefer to look for work rather than prepare themselves to become entrepreneurs. For this reason, it is necessary to foster an interest in entrepreneurship in students from an early age. The purpose of this study was to analyze how the current development of e-commerce influences interest in entrepreneurship, how accounting information systems give students confidence to foster interest in entrepreneurship, how expectations of possible income affect interest in entrepreneurship and how entrepreneurial knowledge possessed by students influences interest in entrepreneurship in student of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri. The approach used is a quantitative approach, which examines the relationship between exogenous variables and endogenous variables. Exogenous variables in this study are E-Commerce, Accounting Information Systems, Income Expectations and Entrepreneurial Knowledge. The endogenous variable is Interest in Entrepreneurship. The study was conducted on students at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri. The research results show that The latent variable of E-commer has a positive and not significant effect on the latent variable of student entrepreneurial interest, The latent variable accounting information system has a positive and significant effect on the latent variable student entrepreneurial interest, The latent variable of income expectations has a negative and not significant effect on the latent variable of student entrepreneurial interest, and The latent variable entrepreneurial knowledge has a positive and significant effect on the latent variable student entrepreneurial interest.

Keywords:- E-Commerce, Accounting Information System, Income Expectations, Entrepreneurial Knowledge, Entrepreneurial Interest.

I. INTRODUCTION

Student graduates are increasing from year to year, and most of these graduates will be looking for work, not preparing themselves to create jobs. This has an impact on increasing the number of unemployed in Indonesia. As the data from BPS of February 2022, the number of unemployed in Indonesia is

5.83% of the working age population of 208.54 million people. Of the 5.83%, 14% came from undergraduate and diploma level graduates (<https://www.unair.ac.id>). Therefore, it is very important to foster an interest in entrepreneurship for students.

Entrepreneurship is one of the important things in supporting the economy of a nation. The economic progress of a nation is influenced by the presence of businesses. That's why the Indonesian government encourages young people to become entrepreneurs. One of the Ministry of Education and Culture's programs to encourage and facilitate students in entrepreneurship is in 2022 in the Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka (MBKM) there is the Merdeka Entrepreneurship program (Program Wirausaha Merdeka - WMK). WMK is part of the MBKM program whose goal is to provide opportunities for students to learn and develop their abilities to become entrepreneurs through activities outside of lectures (<https://kemdikbud.go.id>).

The development of information technology is currently very supportive of businessmen in running their business. Submission of information is faster, easier in transactions, increasing efficiency for businesses. One form of science and technology development that can be utilized by businesses is e-commerce. E-commerce is a form of information technology in the field of buying, selling, marketing goods and services through electronic systems such as the internet, television, or computer networks [1]. E-Commerce provides offers on various types of products ranging from basic needs, fashion, skincare, household appliances, and others. E-commerce is an opportunity for everyone to start their business, because of the convenience in offering products through marketplaces or social media that can reach a broad and unlimited public [2].

Initially, e-commerce was a buying and selling transaction that only used websites and e-mail, but now e-commerce has grown with various forms of marketplaces and social media [3]. From the seller's point of view, with e-commerce it doesn't require a lot of capital to build a store, everyone has the opportunity to become a seller and can reach buyers without any geographical area boundaries. Meanwhile, from the buyer's side, buyers can purchase products online without being limited by distance and working hours. The convenience offered by e-commerce is what supports someone in deciding to become an entrepreneur by selling or offering goods or services through e-commerce. This is contrary to the results of the study [4] which states that e-commerce has no

significant effect on entrepreneurial decision making. However, in line with the results of research conducted by [3], [5], [1], and [2] which states that understanding e-commerce has a significant positive effect on entrepreneurial interest.

An accounting information system is a collection of organizational resources designed in such a way with the aim of facilitating the process of making decisions related to organizational finances. A businessman must understand the accounting information system, because accounting information systems can provide useful information, especially in terms of financial management. A good system can also increase effectiveness and efficiency in business [1]. Furthermore [2] explained that an accounting information system is needed to facilitate the work of businesses in various processes such as collecting and analyzing information or data regarding transactions that occur, so that financial management is more secure. What's more, with current technological developments, using the system will be easier to detect errors than having to do it manually. Therefore, the use of an accounting information system is one of the bases for someone to decide to run a business. This is supported by research results [5], [2], [1], [4] and [3] which states that the use of Accounting Information Systems has a significant positive effect on the interest in entrepreneurship.

In addition to the two factors above, entrepreneurial decisions are also influenced by expected income that may be obtained. According to [5] Income expectation is a person's hope in achieving the target of income from the results of his work. Furthermore [6] states that someone in choosing a job, will not be separated from the income considerations that will be obtained. When someone wants to earn a higher income than having to work as an employee, this is what drives someone to decide to become a businessman. So that the expected income to be received is one of the determining factors for someone deciding to become an entrepreneur. This is contrary to the results of the study [7] which states the opposite, namely income expectations do not affect the interest in entrepreneurship. However, in line with the results of the study [6], [8] and [9] which states that income expectations have a significant effect on entrepreneurial interest.

Furthermore, a person's decision to become an entrepreneur is also influenced by knowledge about entrepreneurship itself. Entrepreneurial knowledge is a process resulting from one's training, experience and understanding, which ultimately makes one brave enough to take risks and read the opportunities around him [10]. Entrepreneurial knowledge is the basis for someone to be an entrepreneur. An entrepreneur will not be successful without having entrepreneurial knowledge, which is followed by the ability and willingness [11]. This is contrary to the results of the study [12] which states that entrepreneurial knowledge has no effect on entrepreneurial decision-making, but is in line with the results of the study [10] and [11] which states that entrepreneurial knowledge has a significant effect on entrepreneurial interest.

The purpose of this study was to analyze whether e-commerce, the use of accounting information systems, income expectations and entrepreneurial knowledge influence the interest in entrepreneurship among students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri.

II. THEORETICAL REVIEW

A. *Entrepreneurial Interest*

Entrepreneurial interest is a tendency for someone to have an interest in having their own business [13]. Entrepreneurial interest is someone's interest, desire, or willingness to work hard to start a business without fear of risk [11]. According to [14] indicators of interest in entrepreneurship are self-confidence, task and result oriented, dare to take risks, have a leadership spirit, and future oriented.

B. *E-Commerce*

E-commerce is a form of information technology in the field of buying, selling, marketing goods and services through electronic systems such as the internet, television, or computer networks [1]. E-commerce provides offers on various types of products ranging from necessities, fashion, skincare, household appliances, and others. E-commerce is an opportunity for everyone to start their business, because of the convenience in offering products through marketplaces or social media that can reach a wide and unlimited public [2]. According to [4] E-commerce indicators include convenience, security guarantees, and service.

C. *Accounting Information System*

An accounting information system is a collection of organizational resources designed in such a way with the aim of facilitating the process of making decisions related to organizational finances. A business person must understand the accounting information system, because accounting information systems can provide useful information, especially in terms of financial management. A good system can also increase effectiveness and efficiency in business [1]. Furthermore [2] explained that an accounting information system is needed to facilitate the work of businesses in various processes such as collecting and analyzing information or data regarding transactions that occur, so that financial management is more secure. Accounting information system indicators according to [4] including effectiveness, efficiency, and reliability.

D. *Income Expectations*

Income expectation is a person's hope in achieving the target income from the results of his work [5]. Furthermore [6] states that someone in choosing a job, will not be separated from the income considerations that will be obtained. When someone wants to earn a higher income than having to work as an employee, and earn unlimited income, this is what drives someone to decide to become a business person. According to [7] income expectation indicators are high income, and unlimited income.

E. Entrepreneurial Knowledge

Entrepreneurial knowledge is a process resulting from one's training, experience and understanding, which ultimately makes one brave enough to take risks and read the opportunities around him [10]. Entrepreneurial knowledge is the basis for someone to be an entrepreneur. An entrepreneur will not be successful without having entrepreneurial knowledge, which is followed by the ability and willingness [11]. Indicator of entrepreneurial knowledge according to [11] including knowledge about the business to be carried out, knowledge about the business environment, knowledge about the roles and responsibilities of businesses, and knowledge about organizational management.

III. METHOD

This research is designed to answer the problems that have been formulated and includes a causality research design,

where the research design is structured to examine the existence of a causal relationship between variables [15]. In this study the approach used is a quantitative approach, which examines the relationship between exogenous variables and endogenous variables. The exogenous variables in this study are E-Commerce, Accounting Information Systems, Income Expectations, and Entrepreneurial Knowledge, as well as the endogenous variable, namely Entrepreneurial Interest. This study was conducted on students at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires consisting of 17 indicators of the Likert scale type with a response of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Before distributing the questionnaires and collecting data, the instruments were distributed to pilot respondents and tested for validity and reliability. The research model that includes 4 exogenous variables with 12 indicators and 1 endogenous variable with 5 indicators is as follows:

Fig 1. Research Model

The population in this study were 1936 students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri, while the sample in this study was 170 students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri. This is based on the sample size that must be met in modeling, namely using a comparison of 5-10 observations for each estimated parameter or indicator [16], meaning that the required sample is 10 times the number of indicators. This study has 17 indicators, so the research sample is determined as many as $10 \times 17 = 170$ students.

The analysis used in testing the model and hypothesis is the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis of the SmartPLS program. Parameter estimation in SEM-PLS is obtained through the following three iteration process stages. First stage: Determine the estimated weight (Weight estimate) used to determine latent variable scores; Second stage: Determine the

estimated path (path estimate) that connects the latent variables and estimates the loading between the latent variables and their indicators; The third stage: Determine the average estimate and parameter locations (regression constant values, intercepts) for indicators and latent variables [17].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The validity of indicators in forming a latent variable is determined by looking at the convergent validity value of the indicators in the model during the evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) through loading factor. If there are any indicators in the model that do not meet the criterion for convergent validity (an absolute loading factor of > 0.7), they are removed from the model. Convergent validity yields the following:

Table 1 Result of Convergent Validity (round 1)

	E-Commer ce	Income Expectations	Entrepreneurial Interest	Entrepreneurial Knowledge	Accounting Information System
x1.1	0.518				
x1.2	0.940				
x1.3	0.923				
x2.1					0.814
x2.2					0.560
x2.3					0.777
x3.1		0.799			
x3.2		0.868			
x4.1				0.729	
x4.2				0.676	
x4.3				0.773	
x4.4				0.708	
y1			0.868		
y2			0.761		
y3			0.222		
y4			0.835		
y5			0.823		

Source: PLS Output

Based on the table 1 above it is known that there are several indicators namely x1.1, x2.2, x4.2, and y3 which have an outer loading value of less than 0.7. Thus, these indicators must be eliminated. The results of convergent validity in the second round are as follows:

Table 2 Result of Convergent Validity (round 2)

	E-Commer ce	Income Expectations	Entre-preneurial Interest	Entre-preneurial Knowledge	Accounting Information System
x1.2	0.955				
x1.3	0.939				
x2.1					0.867
x2.3					0.781
x3.1		0.799			
x3.2		0.868			
x4.1				0.729	

	E-Commerce	Income Expectations	Entre-preneurial Interest	Entre-preneurial Knowledge	Accounting Information System
x4.3				0.760	
x4.4				0.748	
y1			0.876		
y2			0.770		
y4			0.832		
y5			0.819		

Source: PLS Output

According to table 2 of the convergent validity results, all indicators have an outer loading larger than 0.700, hence no indicators should be removed from the model. The average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability can also be used to evaluate the measurement model (outer model). The average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability results are shown below:

Table 3 Result of Average Variance Extracted

	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
E-Commerce	0.946	0.897
Income Expectations	0.821	0.696
Entrepreneurial Interest	0.895	0.681
Entrepreneurial Knowledge	0.790	0.556
Accounting Information System	0.810	0.681

Source: PLS Output

The findings of the average variance extracted (AVE) value and the composite dependability value can be seen in table 5 about result of average variance extracted. The suggested AVE value is larger than 0.5, and the AVE results from this study are known to be over 0.5, implying that the indicator can explain more than half of the variance. Composite reliability is used to assess the consistency or reliability of latent or construct variables. If the composite reliability score is more than 0.7, the latent variable is considered to be reliable. According to table 3, all of the study's latent variables have a composite reliability value of greater than 0.7.

A. Result of Model

Partial least square model for Student Entrepreneurial Interest Faculty of Economics and Business Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri used in this study are as follows:

Table 4 The partial least square student entrepreneurial interest model's estimation results

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDev)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
E-Commerce -> Entrepreneurial Interest	0.106	0.085	1.260	0.208
Income Expectations-> Entrepreneurial Interest	-0.096	0.136	0.707	0.480
Entrepreneurial Knowledge -> Entrepreneurial Interest	0.647	0.112	5.766	0.000
Accounting Information System -> Entrepreneurial Interest	0.212	0.102	2.082	0.038

Source: PLS Output

This study's causation result can also be seen in the figure below:

Fig 2 Model of Student Entrepreneurship Interest

The results estimation of the research model are as follows:

$$y = 0.106x_1 + 0.212x_2 - 0.096x_3 + 0.647x_4$$

It can be observed from the structural equation that:

- The latent variable of E-commers has a positive and not significant effect on the latent variable of student entrepreneurial interest, with path coefficient of 0.106 and p-value of 0.208. As a result, the larger the E-commers, the higher the student entrepreneurial interest, but not significantly.
- The latent variable accounting information system has a positive and significant effect on the latent variable student entrepreneurial interest, with path coefficient of 0.212 and p-value of 0.038. This means that as the accounting information system rises, the student entrepreneurial interest rises as well.
- The latent variable of income expectations has a negative and not significant effect on the latent variable of student entrepreneurial interest, with path coefficient of - 0.096 and p-value of 0.480. As a result, the larger the income expectations, the lower student entrepreneurial interest, but not significantly.
- The latent variable entrepreneurial knowledge has a positive and significant effect on the latent variable student entrepreneurial interest, with path coefficient of 0.647 and p-value of 0.000. This means that as the entrepreneurial knowledge rises, the student entrepreneurial interest rises as well.

B. Discussion

The results of the study show that e-commerce has a positive and insignificant effect on the interest in entrepreneurship of students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri. This shows that the more e-commerce available, the higher the interest in entrepreneurship, but not significant. The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by [4]. The second variable is the accounting information system, the results of the

study show that the accounting information system has a positive and significant effect on the interest in entrepreneurship of students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri. This shows that the increasing accounting information system, the interest in entrepreneurship will also increase. A good system can increase effectiveness and efficiency in business. What's more, with current technological developments, using the system will be easier to detect errors than having to do it manually. Therefore, the use of an accounting information system is one of the bases for someone to decide to run a business. This is supported by research results [5], [2], [1], [4] and [3] which states that the use of Accounting Information Systems has a significant positive effect on the interest in entrepreneurship. The third variable is income expectations, the results of the study show that income expectations have a negative and insignificant effect on the interest in entrepreneurship of students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri. This shows that the higher the expected income, the smaller the interest in entrepreneurship, but not significant. The higher the income earned also shows the higher the risks that must be faced in business. So that income expectations do not significantly influence the interest in entrepreneurship. The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by [7] which states that not everyone thinks that entrepreneurship will generate high income, because income in entrepreneurship fluctuates depending on the high or low demand, the amount of competition and changes in market share. The last variable is entrepreneurial knowledge, the results of the study show that entrepreneurial knowledge has a positive and significant effect on the interest in entrepreneurship of students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri. This shows that the higher the entrepreneurial knowledge, the higher the interest in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial knowledge is the basis for someone to be an entrepreneur. An entrepreneur will not be successful without having entrepreneurial knowledge, which is followed by the ability and willingness. The results of this study are in line with the results of the study [11][10] which states that entrepreneurial knowledge influences the interest in entrepreneurship.

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of the research result shows that the interest in entrepreneurship in students of the Faculty of Economics and Business Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri is influenced by the variables of Accounting Information Systems and Entrepreneurship Knowledge. Meanwhile, the E-Commerce variable and Income Expectations have no significant effect on the interest in entrepreneurship in students of the Faculty of Economics and Business Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri.

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